

Managing Leisure Time on Employee Innovation of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State

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Abstract

The study evaluated the effect of managing leisure time on employee innovation of deposit money banks in Enugu State. The specific objectives of the study are to; examine the effect of networking on the creativity of employees; evaluate the effect of social skills on the improvement of productivity of deposit money banks in Enugu State. The population of the study was Two hundred and eighty two (282) staff of selected banks in Enugu state.. These banks were chosen due to high number of their staff. Simple random method used to give everybody the opportunity of been chosen. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. Two hundred and fifty eight (258) staff returned their questionnaire and accurately filled. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z - test statistic tool. The findings indicated Networking had significant positive effect on the creativity of employees of deposit money banks in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 258), 6.879 < 8.498, P < .05$ and Social skills had significant positive effect on the improvement of productivity of deposit money banks in Enugu State $Z(95, n = 258), 4.233 < 6.698, P < .05$. The study concluded that Networking and Social skills had significant positive effect on the creativity of employees and improvement of productivity of deposit money banks in Enugu State. The study recommended among others that: The bank management should enhance their Networking systems to provide valuable insights into industry trends, which can help, identify new opportunities for growth and innovation.

Keywords Managing Leisure Time; Employee Innovation; Deposit Money Banks; Enugu State

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Introduction

In an everchanging world, the physical and mental attributes of people have changed over time. In this changing and improving world, leisure time concepts and recreation has been a way that people use to protect their physical and mental health. (Demirel, Demirel and Serdar, 2017, Serdar, Demirel, Demirel and Cakir, 2017). Leisure time, defined as the time not dedicated to work or essential tasks, holds subjective meanings for individuals, who engage in diverse activities based on personal preferences and goals (Serdar & Ay, 2016). Managing leisure time effectively involves individuals making intentional choices about how they allocate their free time outside of work commitments to fulfill personal needs and interests (Fişekçioğlu & Özsarı, 2017). In the context of Nigeria's banking sector, where employees face demanding work environments and high-performance expectations, the ability to manage leisure time becomes crucial for maintaining overall well-being and achieving work-life balance (Oladeje & Oyodeye, 2022).

Furthermore, with regards to leisure time management, the significance of effective stress reduction, academic achievement, and socialization has been underscored (Eraniş & Özcan, 2018). However, the impact of leisure time management on employee innovation, particularly within the deposit money banks of Enugu State, Nigeria, remains understudied. Employee innovation, defined as the generation and implementation of novel ideas or solutions to enhance organizational processes or outcomes, is increasingly recognized as a key driver of competitiveness and success in the banking sector (Nkesi, Amah and Olori, 2018). While leisure time management can influence stress levels and overall well-being, its direct relationship with employee innovation remains largely unexplored within the banking context.

In Nigeria's banking sector, characterized by intense market competition and performance pressures, the well-being of employees is integral to organizational success. The ability of employees to manage their leisure time effectively amidst work demands not only impacts their personal lives but also influences their creativity and innovation within the workplace (Oladeje & Oyodeye, 2022). By investigating the effect of managing leisure time on employee innovation in Enugu State's deposit money banks, this study seeks to provide insights into strategies for promoting employee well-being and organizational competitiveness.

Statement of the Problem

In the banking sector in Enugu State, there is a pervasive challenge regarding employee innovation and productivity. Despite the crucial role of leisure time management in fostering creativity and performance, there remains a notable gap in research specifically examining its impact within deposit money banks. The lack of empirical investigation into this relationship hinders the ability of banks to optimize their human capital and adapt to the evolving demands of the market. Furthermore, in the absence of targeted strategies for managing leisure time effectively, banks may struggle to maintain a competitive edge, ultimately compromising their ability to innovate and deliver value to customers.

Aligned with this overarching problem, the objectives of this study are twofold. Firstly, the study aims to explore the effect of networking on the creativity of employees within deposit money banks in Enugu State. Networking is increasingly recognized as a vital component of professional development and innovation, yet its specific influence on employee creativity within the banking sector remains understudied. Secondly, the study seeks to evaluate the impact of social skills on the productivity of deposit money banks in Enugu State. Effective communication and collaboration are essential for organizational success, particularly in client-facing industries such as banking. Understanding how social skills contribute to productivity can inform strategies for talent management and employee development within the banking sector.

Summarily, this study addresses a critical gap in research by investigating the relationship between leisure time management, networking, social skills, and employee innovation within deposit money banks in Enugu State. By examining these factors, the study aims to provide valuable insights that can inform organizational strategies for enhancing employee performance and competitiveness. Ultimately, the findings of this research have the potential to contribute to the overall growth and sustainability of the banking sector in Enugu State, while also advancing scholarly understanding of the intersection between leisure time management, networking, social skills, and innovation in the workplace.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to evaluate the effect of managing leisure time on employee innovation of deposit money banks in Enugu State. The specific objectives of the study are to;

- i. Examine the effect of networking on the creativity of employees of deposit money banks in Enugu State.
- ii. Evaluate the effect of social skills on the improvement of productivity of deposit money banks in Enugu State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

- i. What is the effect of networking on the creativity of employees of deposit money banks in Enugu State?
- ii. What is the effect of social skills on the improvement of productivity of deposit money banks in Enugu State?

Statement of Hypotheses

The following hypotheses guided the study;

- i. Networking has effect on the creativity of employees of deposit money banks in Enugu State.
- ii. Social skills have effect on the improvement of productivity of deposit money banks in Enugu State.

Significance of the Study

This study holds substantial significance for various stakeholders within the banking sector in Enugu State. For deposit money banks, the findings offer valuable insights into the factors influencing employee innovation and productivity, particularly in relation to leisure time management, networking, and social skills. By understanding these dynamics, banks can implement targeted strategies to enhance employee performance, foster a culture of innovation, and ultimately improve organizational effectiveness and competitiveness. Employees stand to benefit from a deeper understanding of how networking and social skills impact their creativity and productivity, empowering them to cultivate these competencies for personal and professional growth. Additionally, policymakers and regulatory bodies in the banking sector can use the study's findings to inform policy decisions aimed at promoting employee well-being and fostering a conducive work environment conducive to innovation and productivity. Overall, the study's significance lies in its potential to drive positive change and improve outcomes for all stakeholders involved in the banking industry in Enugu State.

Review of Related Literature

Conceptual Review

Managing Leisure Time

Leisure management is an important tool in ensuring the balance of work (lesson/study), which is interpreted as having enough time to meet the responsibilities of the individual both in his spare time and study. Leisure management; is a type of time management that occurs with the effective implementation of time management. Individuals who realize the study time and the time allocated for leisure time will be able to get a distance in providing the balance in question more easily (Durhan, 2020). Fişekçioğlu and Özsarı (2017) have defined leisure management as the intentional and structured utilization of time beyond work commitments to fulfill personal needs. According to Polat et al. (2019), individuals have the flexibility to assess their leisure activities according to their interests, requirements, and anticipations. Leisure time in free time is expressed as the actions of freedom of the individual. According to Akgul et. al (2015), leisure time; expresses the time required by the good planning and evaluation of the time as a time period that human beings can freely use in order to be able to play, relax, have fun or improve themselves in accordance with their tendencies and wishes.

Networking

Networking refers to the process of establishing and nurturing relationships with individuals and groups for mutual benefit, often within a professional or social context. It encompasses various activities such as building connections, exchanging information, seeking advice, and creating opportunities for collaboration or advancement (Kagan, 2022). Network capability is a dynamic capability that creates dependencies inside and outside the organization (Battistella et al. 2017). Networking capabilities enable companies to gain access to disparate resources, identify opportunities and respond quickly to ever-changing marketing needs (Solano et al. 2018). This variable is a company ability to develop and utilize interactions between organizations in order to gain access to various resources owned by other parties. According to Zacca et al. (2015) network capability is the company's ability to create, improve, and use the organization's internal and external relationships.

Social Skills

Social skills refer to the manner of behavior demonstrated in social settings. Put simply, these skills entail the ability to exhibit behaviors that are beneficial for both individuals and the community as a whole. Individuals typically engage and continue to interact with family, friends, and close social circles. Possessing adequate social skills is essential for effective and rewarding interaction within these contexts (Gokel and Dagli, 2017). Social skills can be grouped into 4 types of skills which are namely survival, interpersonal, problem solving and conflict resolution skills. Survival skills can be defined as the skills which include obeying rules and following directions. In addition, listening orders and suggestions are also included in these skills. Interpersonal skills on the other hand include skills such as empathy, learning collaboratively, sharing and relationships. Problem solving skills, differently, includes skills such as responsibility taking, help requesting, decision making and independence seeking. Finally, conflict resolution skills include skills such as coping with difficulties and apologising. These skills also include internal peace of the people where the conflict mostly occurs (Johnson, 2016).

Employee Innovation

Innovation is a change that offers newness from an existing product or service (Panchbudhe et al. 2021). Generally, innovation can be understood as the introduction of novelty. Innovation is the embodiment, combination, or synthesis of knowledge about new products, processes, or services that are original, relevant, and valued (Kahn, 2018). Innovativeness of employees is measured by the propensity by which they innovate in their work; their willingness to try new ways which are different from the existing; the enthusiasm to adopt new ideas or new methods to their work operation; and the eagerness to implement the innovation strategy in their work. Employee innovativeness refers to employees' propensity to innovate can be conceived as complex behaviour consisting of idea generation, idea promotion and idea realization with Employee innovativeness refers to employees' propensity to innovate can be conceived as complex behavior consisting of idea generation, idea promotion and idea realization with the aim of meeting organizational goals in novel ways (Enenifa and Akintokumbo, 2020; Mbah & Diele, 2020).

Creativity

Creativity is defined as the ability to present new perspectives, to generate new and meaningful ideas. Creativity can also mean employees use their diverse skills, abilities, knowledge, views and experiences to generate new ideas for decision making, problem solving and task completion in an efficient manner (Kremer et al. 2019; Eze, et al., 2020). Otherwise according to Lee & Kim (2021), Creativity is a person's ability to create something different, both in the form of results that can be assessed and in the form of ideas (actions that produce new and different creative works). Employee creativity can be interpreted as central to the long-term survival of an organization because employees can generate new and potentially useful ideas for creating new, or improving existing, products, services, processes, and routines (Akgunduz et al. 2018). Creativity can also mean employees use their diverse skills, abilities, knowledge, views and experiences to generate new ideas for decision making, problem solving and task completion in an efficient manner (Newman et al. 2018; and Ugwu & Mbah, 2018)

Improved Productivity

Productivity is a relationship between outputs and inputs. It rises when an increase in output occurs with less than proportionate increase in inputs, or when the same output is produced with fewer inputs (ILO, 2005). Productivity

can also be considered in monetary terms. If the price received for an output rises with no increase in the cost of inputs, this is also seen as an increase in productivity. Productivity improvements can be understood at different levels. Staff productivity may be reflected in employment rates, wage rates, stability of employment, job satisfaction or employability across jobs or industries (Chukwuma, 2022). Okochi and Ateke (2021) construe staff productivity as employees' efforts, demonstrated in the outcome of goods and services they produced and how these conform to standards, are free of errors, less wasteful and does not require rework.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Linkages Between Study Variables

The diagram above shows how the variables of the study are linked with each other. The diagram shows the path of effect running from the independent variable, the different components of the independent variable to the components of the dependent variable in the study. The diagram shows that an increase in networking improves creativity, while an increase in social skills improves productivity as well, with regards to the objective of the study.

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on the Social Exchange Theory of Homans. This is because the theory provides a framework for understanding how employees may engage in leisure time activities within the workplace based on the perceived benefits they expect to receive.

Social Exchange Theory

Social Exchange Theory was founded by George C. Homans in 1958. This theory posits that social behavior is the result of an exchange process, where individuals seek to maximize rewards and minimize costs in their interactions with others (Homans, 1958). The theory suggests that individuals engage in relationships and social interactions based on the perceived benefits they will receive in return. These benefits can include tangible rewards such as money or goods, as well as intangible rewards such as social approval or emotional support. Additionally, Social Exchange Theory assumes that individuals are rational actors who make decisions based on the anticipated outcomes of their actions (Thibaut & Kelley, 1959).

Social Exchange Theory is relevant to the study as it provides a framework for understanding how employees may engage in leisure time activities within the workplace based on the perceived benefits they expect to receive. For example, employees may participate in networking events or engage in recreational activities with colleagues if they believe it will lead to increased job satisfaction or career advancement opportunities. By applying Social Exchange Theory, the study can explore how employees weigh the costs and benefits of managing their leisure time and how this influences their innovation and productivity within deposit money banks in Enugu State.

Empirical Review

Networking and Creativity

Aurengzeb, Haidar and Amir (2018) examined the impact of recreational activities on the employee productivity and for this the total of 350 sample is occupied from the bank's employee of Karachi Pakistan. The methodology of this research is quantitative in nature. The data is collected through non-probability convenience sampling that was tasted on SPSS statistical software however, technique used to collect data is a close ended questionnaire. There were three independent variables and one dependent variables. The independent variables are physical fitness, mental fitness and entertainment activities and dependent variables is job satisfaction. The finding through this research revealed that the independent variable effects positivity on the dependent variable.

Enenifa (2020) examined the relationship between workplace recreational activities and employee effectiveness in Deposit Money Banks in Yenogoa, Bayelsa State. The study adopted a cross-sectional survey in its investigation of the variables. Primary data was generated through structured questionnaire. The population of the study was 277 employees of nineteen (19) Deposit Money Banks in Yenogoa, Bayelsa State. The sample size of 164 was determined using the Taro Yamane's formula for sample size determination. The reliability of the instrument was achieved by the use of the Cronbach Alpha coefficient with all the items scoring above 0.70. The hypotheses were tested using the Spearman's Rank Order Correlation Statistics. The tests were carried out at a 95% confidence interval and a 0.05 level of significance. Findings from the data analysis revealed that there is a significant the relationship between workplace recreational activities rand employee effectiveness in Deposit Money Banks in Yenogoa, Bayelsa State. The study recommended that management of Deposit Money Banks should create avenues for workplace recreational activities for its employees because it not only polishes the employee skills but also prepare them to accomplish the current and future challenging assignments.

Wang, et al. (2022) investigated the consequences of enterprise social media usage. It investigates how enterprise social media usage influences employee creativity. A moderated mediation model is developed based on social exchange theory. The empirical sample of 238 employees is used to test the proposed model. Results of the empirical analysis performed using PROCESS macro of SPSS indicate that enterprise social media usage positively impacts employee creativity via the mediating mechanisms (i.e., leader-member exchange and support for innovation). Furthermore, social media usage frequency negatively moderates this impact of enterprise social media usage on employee creativity via leader-member exchange. Interestingly, the empirical analysis reveals that the impact of enterprise social media usage frequency strengthens the indirect effect that enterprise social media usage has on employee creativity via perceived support for innovation.

Sari and Arief (2022) determined factors that can affect firm performance. This research is conducted with a quantitative approach with the subject being the service users of newcomer IT manufactures companies as many as 75 companies with 200 respondents. The analysis technique uses a Structural Equation Model (SEM) approach with smart PLS. The results in this study indicate that digital innovation, network capability, and marketing performance affect firm performance but customer relationship management does not. In addition, innovation and customer relationship management affect marketing performance but network capability does not. Other than that, marketing performance can moderate digital innovation and firm performance, customer relationship management and firm performance but cannot on network capability and firm performance. It means that digital innovation, network capability, and marketing performance need maintaining in order to increase the firm performance. Therefore, any company needs to determine the significant factors to reach the advantages. In addition, because this research only focuses on several factors such as digital innovation, network capability, marketing performance, and customer relationship, other research that involves several factors that can increase firm performance needs to be conducted.

Hassan, Malik and Hasnain (2023) investigated the role of contextual factors such as job complexity and relationship with supervisor on employee creativity that in turn have positive effect on firm's innovation and performance. This study further investigates that employee intrinsic motivation mediates the relationship between contextual factors and employee creativity. Data were collected through convenient sampling from banking employees working in different branches of seven Pakistani banks operating in Multan city through 164 questionnaires which then analyzed using SPSS 16. Descriptive statistics and correlation analysis were employed in the study. The results showed the direct relationship of job complexity and supervisory relationship with employee creativity keeping the mediating variable unaffected. Further, employee creativity has shown significant positive relation with organization innovation capability and firm performance. Managerial implications, limitations and recommendations for future research have also been discussed.

Social Skills and Productivity

Inge, Mochamad and Ayu (2020) investigated the effect of “Work-life balance and emotional intelligence have an impact on turnover intention in Indonesia, with organizational commitment acting as an intervening variable. The descriptive approach of research was employed in this study. The overall population of this study consisted of all 60 employees of PT Grafitama Deltakreasi. Employees of a company that distributes computer parts, with a sample size of 60 respondents. Structural equation model (SEM) with Smart-PLS analysis tool 3.2.8 was the method employed in this study. The findings demonstrate that organizational commitment was positively and significantly impacted by work-life balance. Organizational commitment was significantly and favorably impacted by emotional intelligence. Work-life balance significantly and negatively impacted the intention to leave one’s job. Finally, organizational commitment had a negative and substantial impact on turnover intention, while emotional intelligence had a favorable and significant impact.

Sangperm, Sangperm and Aramrueang (2021) examined the role of self-motivation and social skills to enhance the performance. Therefore, the relationship between self-motivation, social skills and performance was examined by the current study. A survey was carried out for data collection from Thailand. Thai court judges were the respondents of the study. By using a questionnaire survey, 200 questionnaires were used for data collection. Finally, data was used for analysis through statistical tool, namely, Partial Least Square (PLS). Results of the study found that self-motivation has positive effect on performance and social skills. Moreover, social skills have positive effect on performance. Finally, it is found that social skills mediate the relationship between self-motivation and performance.

Chukwuma (2022) investigated the relationship between organizational change and staff productivity of deposit money banks in Port Harcourt. The study employed cross-sectional research design. The population of the study consist 21 deposit money banks. Primary data was collected from 202 management level staff using a five-point scaled questionnaire. The Spearman’s Rank Order correlation served as the test statistic. The Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 23.0 was relied upon for all data analyses. The study found a strong connection between organizational change (represented as technological change and structural change) and staff productivity (represented as effective efficiency and staff engagement) of deposit money banks in Port Harcourt. The study therefore concludes that productivity of deposit money banks’ employees can be improved through organizational change, and recommends that management deposit money banks’ that desire improved productivity of employees should design and implement organizational change.

Okpabi, et al. (2024) examined the effect of work life balance on organizational performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study concentrated on the employees of a few selected deposit money institutions in the 606-person Makurdi metropolis. The Taro Yamane formula was used to calculate the sample size, which resulted in a sample size of 252 people. The study used first-hand information. The major data collection tool was a questionnaire. Regression and correlation analysis were the methods utilized to analyze the data, and the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS 21) was used to assess the hypotheses that were developed. Tables and straightforward percentages were used to portray the raw data that was taken from the primary source. The study found that work-life balance issues, family responsibilities, and flexible work schedules all benefited certain deposit money institutions in the Makurdi metropolis. The study’s ultimate finding is that effective wellness initiatives offered by banks are essential for raising staff productivity and organizational effectiveness.

Summary of Empirical Reviewed Literature

Based on the empirical studies provided, a notable gap in knowledge emerges regarding the specific impact of leisure time management on employee innovation and productivity within the banking sector, particularly in Enugu State. While some studies have explored related concepts such as recreational activities (Aurengzeb, Haidar, & Amir, 2018), workplace recreational activities (Enenifa, 2020), and work-life balance (Salolomo & Agbaeze, 2019; Okpabi et al., 2024), there is a lack of research directly addressing how leisure time management influences employee creativity and effectiveness in Enugu State's banking industry. Existing studies predominantly focus on factors such as social skills, organizational change, and technological innovation (Sari & Arief, 2022; Hassan, Malik, & Hasnain, 2023; Chukwuma, 2022), but fail to specifically examine the role of leisure time management in enhancing employee innovation and productivity. Therefore, there is a notable gap in understanding the relationship between leisure time management and employee outcomes within the context of Enugu State's banking sector, necessitating further

empirical investigation to fill this gap and provide comprehensive insights into effective strategies for promoting employee innovation and productivity in this setting.

Methodology

The area of the study was Enugu State. The population of the study was Two hundred and eighty two (282) staff of selected banks in Enugu state. These banks were chosen due to high number of their staff. Simple random method used to give everybody the opportunity of been chosen. The study used the descriptive survey design approach. The primary source of data was the administration of questionnaire. Two hundred and fifty eight (258) staff returned their questionnaire and accurately filled. That gave 92 percent response rate. The validity of the instrument was tested using content analysis and the result was good. The reliability was tested using the Pearson correlation coefficient (r). It gave a reliability co-efficient of 0.81 which was also good. Data was presented and analyzed by mean score and standard deviation using Sprint Likert Scale. The hypotheses were analyzed using Z - test statistic tool.

Data Presentation and Analyses

The effect of networking on the creativity of employees of deposit money banks in Enugu State.

Table 1: Responses on the effect of networking on the creativity of employees of deposit money banks in Enugu State

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Networking makes new relationships and promotes flexibility.	490 98 42.1	408 102 28.9	39 13 9.8	38 19 8.5	26 26 10.6	1001 258 100%	3.88	1.274	Agree
2	Fostering of existing customers are enhances with networking which generates results.	550 110 42.6	364 91 35.3	39 13 5.0	18 9 3.5	35 35 13.6	1006 258 100%	3.90	1.354	Agree
3	Access to information through networking promotes independence and freedom.	465 93 36.0	328 82 31.8	69 23 8.9	40 20 7.8	40 40 15.5	942 258 100%	3.65	1.429	Agree
4	There is diversity of thought with networking and increases in innovation.	595 119 46.1	220 55 21.3	87 29 11.2	24 12 4.7	43 43 16.7	969 258 100%	3.76	1.486	Agree
5	Access to job opportunities is promoted through networking which helps active involvement.	400 124 48.1	320 54 20.9	75 31 12.0	48 10 3.9	26 39 15.1	869 258 100%	3.83	1.448	Agree
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.804	1.3982	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 1, 200 respondents out of 258 representing 71.0 percent agreed that Networking makes new relationships and promotes flexibility 3.88 and standard deviation of 1.274. Fostering of existing customers are enhances with networking which generates results 201 respondents representing 77.9 percent agreed with mean score of 3.90 and standard deviation of 1.354. Access to information through networking promotes independence and freedom 175 respondents representing 67.8 percent agreed with mean score of 3.65 and standard deviation of 1.429. There is diversity of thought with networking and increases in innovation 174 respondents representing 67.4 percent agreed with mean score of 3.76 and 1.486. Access to job opportunities is promoted through networking which helps active involvement 178 respondents representing 69.0 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.83 and standard deviation 1.448.

The Effect of Social Skills on the Improvement of Productivity of Deposit Money Banks in Enugu State

Table 2: Responses on the effect of social skills on the improvement of productivity of deposit money banks in Enugu State

		5	4	3	2	1	ΣFX	-	SD	Decision
		SA	A	N	DA	SD		X		
1	Communication flow in the bank increases the output.	435	204	189	18	48	888	3.47		Agree
		87	51	63	9	48	258		1.455	
		33.7	19.8	24.4	3.5	18.6	100%			
2	The relationship skills helps banks expansion	405	364	75	44	39	927	3.59		Agree
		81	91	25	22	39	258		1.398	
		31.4	35.3	9.7	8.5	15.1	100%			
3	Prompt conflict resolution in the bank promotes growth.	490	284	102	20	45	941	3.65		Agree
		98	71	34	10	45	258		1.456	
		38.0	27.5	13.2	3.9	17.4	100%			
4	Good interaction skills in the bank attraction more customers.	515	272	117	16	40	960	3.72		Agree
		103	68	39	8	40	258		1.414	
		39.9	26.4	15.1	3.1	15.5	100%			
5	Active listening enhances customer's retention.	250	272	237	26	48	695	3.23		Agree
		50	68	79	13	48	258		1.337	
		19.4	26.4	30.6	5.0	18.6	100%			
Total Grand mean and standard deviation								3.532	1.412	

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 2, 138 respondents out of 258 representing 53.5 percent agreed that Communication flow in the bank increases the output 3.47 and standard deviation of 1.455. The relationship skills helps banks expansion 172 respondents representing 66.7 percent agreed with mean score of 3.59 and standard deviation of 1.398. Prompt conflict resolution in the bank promotes growth 169 respondents representing 65.5 percent agreed with mean score of 3.65 and standard deviation of 1.456. Good interaction skills in the bank attraction more customers 171 respondents representing 66.3 percent agreed with mean score of 3.72 and 1.414. Active listening enhances customer's retention 118 respondents representing 45.8 percent agreed with a mean score of 3.23 and standard deviation 1.337.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One: Networking has effect on the creativity of employees of deposit money banks in Enugu State

Table 3: One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test						
		Networking makes new relationships and promotes flexibility.	Fostering of existing customers are enhances with networking which generates results.	Access to information through networking promotes independence and freedom.	There is diversity of thought with networking and increases in innovation.	Access to job opportunities is promoted through networking which helps active involvement.
N		258	258	258	258	258
Uniform Parameter $s^{a,b}$	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Difference s	Absolute	.525	.529	.428	.461	.481
	Positive	.101	.136	.155	.167	.151
	Negative	-.525	-.529	-.428	-.461	-.481
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		8.436	8.498	6.879	7.409	7.720
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value of $6.879 < 8.498$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that networking had significant positive effect on the creativity of employees of deposit money banks in Enugu State.

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value of $6.879 < 8.498$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 95percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that networking had significant positive effect on the creativity of employees of deposit money banks in Enugu State.

Hypothesis Two: Social skills have effect on the improvement of productivity of deposit money banks in Enugu State

		Communication flow in the bank increases the output.	The relationship skills helps banks expansion	Prompt conflict resolution in the bank promotes growth.	Good interaction skills in the bank attraction more customers.	Active listening enhances customer's retention.
N		258	258	258	258	258
Uniform Parameters ^{a,b}	Minimum	1	1	1	1	1
	Maximum	5	5	5	5	5
Most Extreme Differences	Absolute	.337	.417	.405	.413	.264
	Positive	.186	.151	.174	.155	.186
	Negative	-.337	-.417	-.405	-.413	-.264
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		5.416	6.693	6.506	6.630	4.233
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
a. Test distribution is Uniform.						
b. Calculated from data.						

Decision Rule

If the calculated Z-value is greater than the critical Z-value (i.e $Z_{cal} > Z_{critical}$), reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis accordingly.

Result

With Kolmogorov-Smirnon Z – value of $4.233 < 6.698$ and on Asymp. Significance of 0.000, the responses from the respondents as display in the table is normally distributed. This affirms the assertion of the most of the respondents that social skills had significant positive effect on the improvement of productivity of deposit money banks in Enugu State.

Decision

Furthermore, comparing the calculated Z- value of $4.233 < 6.698$ against the critical Z- value of .000 (2-tailed test at 95percent level of confidence) the null hypothesis were rejected. Thus, the alternative hypothesis was accepted which states that social skills had significant positive effect on the improvement of productivity of deposit money banks in Enugu State.

Discussion of Findings

From the result of hypothesis one, the calculated Z- value of $6.879 < 8.498$ against the critical Z- value of .000 which implies that Networking had significant positive effect on the creativity of employees of deposit money banks in Enugu State. In the support of the result in the literature review, Wang, et al. (2022) investigated the consequences of enterprise social media usage. Interestingly, the empirical analysis reveals that the impact of enterprise social media usage frequency strengthens the indirect effect that enterprise social media usage has on employee creativity via perceived support for innovation. Hassan, Malik and Hasnain (2023) investigated the role of contextual factors such as job complexity and relationship with supervisor on employee creativity that in turn have positive effect on firm’s innovation and performance. This study further investigates that employee intrinsic motivation mediates the relationship between contextual factors and employee creativity. The results showed the direct relationship of job complexity and supervisory relationship with employee creativity keeping the mediating variable unaffected.

From the result of hypothesis two, the calculated Z- value of $4.233 < 6.698$ against the critical Z- value of .000 which implies that social skills had significant positive effect on the improvement of productivity of deposit money banks

in Enugu State. In the support of the result in the literature review, Inge, Mochamad and Ayu (2020) investigated the effect of "Work-life balance and emotional intelligence have an impact on turnover intention in Indonesia, with organizational commitment acting as an intervening variable. The findings demonstrate that organizational commitment was positively and significantly impacted by work-life balance. Organizational commitment was significantly and favorably impacted by emotional intelligence. Sangperm, Sangperm and Aramrueang (2021) examined the role of self-motivation and social skills to enhance the performance. Results of the study found that self-motivation has positive effect on performance and social skills. Okpabi, et al. (2024) examined the effect of work life balance on organizational performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria. The study found that work-life balance issues, family responsibilities, and flexible work schedules all benefited certain deposit money institutions in the Makurdi metropolis.

Summary of Findings

- i. Networking had significant positive effect on the creativity of employees of deposit money banks in Enugu State, $Z(95, n = 258), 6.879 < 8.498, P < .05$
- ii. Social skills had significant positive effect on the improvement of productivity of deposit money banks in Enugu State $Z(95, n = 258), 4.233 < 6.698, P < .05$

Conclusion

The study concluded that Networking and Social skills had significant positive effect on the creativity of employees and improvement of productivity of deposit money banks in Enugu State. Engaging in leisure activities reduces stress levels, improves mood, enhancing creativity, and increasing productivity. Leisure time again provides an opportunity for employees to develop other important life skills, such as time management, self-discipline, and self-awareness. Leisure time not only relieves boredom and stress but also promotes one's physical and emotional health. It gives rest to a person's mind from daily stress when he takes time to focus on enjoyable leisure activities. This allows him to be more focused when the time comes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study recommended that:

- i. The bank management should enhance their Networking systems to provide valuable insights into industry trends, which can help, identify new opportunities for growth and innovation.
- ii. The success of the bank depends on the Social skills of the staff, therefore there should be effective need to communicate more effectively and efficiently and, as a result, build, maintain and grow relationships with colleagues, clients and new contacts.

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